

School of Engineering,
Madan Bhandari Memorial Academy Nepal,
Joint Constituent College of Pokhara University

Annual Report
For
Research and Development Activities of 2078/79 and Proposed Activities for 2079/80

SUBMITTED BY
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Introduction

Madan Bhandari Memorial Academy (MBMAN), a non-profit Non-Government Organization (NGO) came into existence in 1993 to materialize the concept of the great visionary legend Hon. Madan Bhandari, in Morang district of Eastern Nepal which is devoted in upgrading the life standard of people especially of poor, backward, marginalized and socially excluded citizens through community program and technical education. We have different schools at MBMAN.

School of Nursing Bhadrapur is dedicated to serve the nation by producing 40 qualified nurses every year.

PCL General Medicine, Community Medicine Assistant (CMA), Auxiliary Nurse Midwifery (ANM) are offered at Polytechnic Institute, Tarabari, Jhapa

School Of Agriculture is offering Diploma level Agriculture courses in Plant science and Animal science and TSLC level course Animal Health/Livestock production (Vet JTA) along with extensive research

We are offering Engineering from Technical SLC to Masters Level; Civil Sub-Overseer, Diploma in Civil Engineering, BE Civil, BE Computer, B.Arc and M.Sc Construction Management.

Vision:

“Self-Reliance and Cultured Society ”

Mission:

“Technology Transformation Is Academy Concern; Right Based Program Is Our Foundation.”

Goal

“The Academy Developed As A Reliable Centre For Hope and Trust for The Targeted Community.”

Objectives

The Academy Takes Pride In Its Concept And Principle “Right-Holders Are Progressing Towards Improved Living Standards Through Better Technology, Skills And Resource Mobilization”.

Specific Objectives:

- To conduct employment based technical and vocational skill training, to develop skilled technical human resource targeting national and international market.
- To build upon the traditional skills and appropriate technology and transformation for productivity and self-employment.

- To support natural resource management and in development and management of enterprises based on the use of local human resources.
- To undertake studies, research and publication works in relation to the technical and vocational training organized by the academy, as well as in different public issues and their socio-economic impact.
- To support and facilitate implementation of programs on Human Rights and Right Based Approach for Social Transformation and justice.
- To undertake study and research on ideology, philosophy and thoughts of the visionary leader Madan Kumar Bhandari, their documentation, publication, extension and safe custody and
- To initiate for the promotion of Technological University for developing skilled human resource through higher technical education, research and equivalence.

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We are offering research based BE Civil, BE Computer, B. Arc. and M.Sc. Construction Management under the affiliation of Pokhara University. During bachelor, students are doing group research work and at master level, students are conducting independent research work. The function of research in effective teaching and that of teaching on efficient research has been validated to be noticeably critical. Many colleges and all universities round the sector have already adopted the ‘teaching cum research’ version. Madan Bhandari Memorial Academy Nepal is likewise within the technique to achieve this aim. Establishment of Madan Bhandari Research Centre (MBRC) turned into a leap forward on this path under the guidance of Pokhara University. MBRC is aimed at offering research allowing environment, motivation and support in research for students and faculties by way of clean studies policy and green administrative approaches. MBRC policy and hints are so designed as to mirror the vision and purpose set through Pokhara University and MBMAN on the basis of its beyond studies, available information, and future planned activities. Our effort can be to simplify the manner of offers management inside the framework of University rules and regulations. We desire that our endeavor will lead MBMAN to the point in which the colleges generate new knowledge and apply it to help government as well as the community for quicker vision inside the use of MBMAN.

Madan Bhandari Research Management Cell operated at School of Engineering has been formulated as per regulatory provisions of Pokhara University. The RMC is trying to bring students, faculty and society together at its research platform.

Research and Development Activities of 2078/79

Following are the research activities performed during the year 2078/79.

1. Training Conducted: A 2 days training conducted for effective research conduction by Ananda Nepal who is Chief of Students Recruitment and Lecture of Kcg (The Kyoto College of Graduate Studies for Informatics) Kyoto, Japan
He is working applied IT Professional and Academic Coordinator Of Web System Development and Mankeshwar Thakur, Technical Auditor.
2. Workshop:
 - A. One day workshop conducted for generating local research issue among public representative of Morang and Jhapa by RMC.
 - B. Computer Engineering Workshop: To Develop Your Career Path for One day
 - C. 3 Days workshop on Python Programming
3. Formation of Youth incubation Centre: In collaboration with Provincial government and Madan Bhandari Memorial Academy Nepal, School of Entrepreneurship Development

has been established with an objective of involving youth for incubation of business society through application of technology to foster competitive business. The project work of students will be tried to be consumed among business society for taking the business at new height.

4. Joint Faculty Research

Research Project	Research Member	Status	Publications
project Performance	<p>Dr. A.K. Mishra (TL)</p> <p>Dr. Sudarsan J.S invited Professor (Assistant) from National Institute of Construction Management and Research Centre , India and Dr. Subramanian Nithiyananantham, SRM Institute of Science and Technology</p> <p>Dr. P.S. Aithal(VC of Srinivas University as invited)</p> <p>Er. Amrit Dahal (Invited)</p> <p>Er. Joseph Rana Rai(Student), Om Prakash Chaudhary(Student)</p>	ongoing: Students have been additionally deployed	<p>[1] https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s42108-022-00195-z</p> <p>[2] https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s13762-022-04017-x</p> <p>[3] Mishra, A.K. (2021). Assessment Of Grid Electric Powered Transformation Into Solar Powered Pumping Water Supply Projects. Nat. Volatiles &Essent. Oils, 2021; 8(6): 1533-1546</p> <p>[4] Mishra, A. K., & Aithal, P. S., (2022). Performance Assessment of Irrigation: A Casefrom Nepal-Asia. International Journal of Management, Technology, and Social Sciences(IJMTS), 7(1), 444-464. DOI: https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6657541</p> <p>[5] Mishra, A.K., & Dahal, A.K, EFFECTS OF DESIGN REVIEW OF SELECTED IRRIGATIONPROJECTS FROM DANG VALLEY, NEPAL-ASIA, frican Journal of Applied ResearchVol. 8, No. 1 (2022), pp. 39-62http://www.ajaronline.comhttp://doi.org/10.26437/ajar.03.2022.3</p> <p>[6] Mishra, A.K. (2022).“Evaluate the Farmers’Participation forIrrigation Developmentin Nepal ”, InternationalSocial Mentality andResearcher ThinkersJournal, (Issn:2630-631X) 8(57): 630-644</p> <p>[7] Dahal, Amrit Kumar., Mishra, A. K., & Aithal, P. S. (2022). Operation of Design Reviewin Small Irrigation Projects in Dang Valley of Nepal. International Journal of Case Studiesin Business, IT, and Education (IJCSBE), 6(1), 139-157. DOI:https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6331334</p> <p>[8] Mishra, A. K., & Aithal, P. S., (2022). Planning Assessment of Transport System: A Casefrom Nepal. International Journal of Applied Engineering and Management Letters(IJAEML), 6(1), 280-300. DOI: https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6577822</p> <p>[9] Mishra, A. K., & Aithal, P. S., (2022). Cost-Effective Design of Latrine for Low IncomeGroup. International Journal of Management, Technology, and Social Sciences (IJMTS),7(1), 306-321. DOI: https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6463468</p>

			<p>[10] Mishra, A. K., & Aithal, P. S., (2022). Effectiveness of Arbitration in Construction Projects. International Journal of Management, Technology, and Social Sciences(IJMTS), 7(1), 96-111. DOI: https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6246129</p> <p>[11] Mishra, A. K., & Aithal, P. S., (2022). Causes and Effects of Design Change of Construction Projects. International Journal of Applied Engineering and Management Letters (IAEML), 6(1), 87-99. DOI: https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6085346</p>
Assessment of Compact Minkowski Fractal Microstrip Filter for Band Applications	<p>Dr. A.K. Mishra (TL)</p> <p>Er. Manoj Kumar Singh (Invited from PU)</p> <p>Er. Chandan Bhagat</p> <p>Mr. Dipak Gautam</p>	Completed and Published	<p>A.K.Mishra, M.K.Singh, D.Gautam, C.Bhagat. (2022). Assessment of Compact Minkowski Fractal Microstrip Filter for Band Applications. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6538787</p>
Model for Effective Implementation of e-Government Services in Province 1 Nepal	<p>Er. Chandan Bhagat (TL)</p> <p>Dr. A.K. Mishra</p>	Completed and 2 articles published and one working paper is ready to be submitted: Model for Effective Implementation of e-Government Services in Developing Countries like Nepal	<p>[1] Chandan Bhagat, Bharat Sharma, & Anjay Kumar Mishra. (2021). CRITICAL SUCCESS FACTORS FOR THE IMPLEMENTATION OF E-GOVERNANCE - A CASE STUDY OF PROVINCE 1 NEPAL. International Journal of Interdisciplinary Research in Arts and Humanities (IJIRAH), 6(1), 22-26. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4771690</p> <p>[2] Chandan Bhagat et al; East African Scholars J Eng Comput Sci; Vol-4, Iss-4 (May, 2021): 46-52</p> <p>[3] Model for Effective Implementation of e-Government Services in Developing Countries like Nepal</p>
Development of n-variable Regression Model	<p>Mr. K.K. Chaudhary (TL)</p> <p>Dr. A.K. Mishra</p>	Completed and published 3 Articles even applied for Intellectual Property Rights from Government of	<p>[1] Chaudhary KK, Mishra AK. Development of n-variable Regression Model. J Adv Res Appl Math Stat 2021; 6(1&2): 1-3</p> <p>[2] Chaudhary, Krishna Kumar, & Mishra, Anjay Kumar, (2021). Analysis of GDP using then-variable Regression Model. International Journal of Management, Technology, and Social Sciences (IJMTS), 6(1), 170-175. DOI: https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4772970</p>

		India	[3] Krishna Kumar Chaudhary, Anjay Kumar Mishra Validation of n-variable Linear Regression Model. NOLEGEIN Journal of Operations Research & Management. 2021; 4(2): 26–29p
Rain Water harvesting	Er. Gokul Dev Joshi (TL) Dr. A.K. Mishra	Ongoing : Additional members are under process of deployment	Anjay Kumar Mishra & Er. Gokul Dev Joshi, “Prospects of Rooftop Rain water Harvesting: A Case from Nepal”, Indo American Journal of Multidisciplinary Research and Review, Volume 5, Issue 1, Page Number 31-35, 2021.
Lean Construction	Dr. A.K. Mishra (TL) Dr. P.S. Aithal (VC of Srinivas University as invited)	Ongoing: Additional Members are under the process of deployment. Even Ph.D. scholar are interested to join as invited member	Mishra, A. K., & Aithal, P. S., (2022). Assessing the Magnitude of Waste Material Using Lean Construction. International Journal of Case Studies in Business, IT, and Education (IJCSBE), 6(1), 578-589. DOI: https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6717736
Virtual Agriculture IT Industry	Not Started	Ananda Nepal will be invited expert.	A team will be formed from MBMAN faculties of IT and Agriculture to start it immediately after assurance of project Financing.
Economic Construction	Dr. A. K. Mishra (TL) Mr. Madan Sharma, P.Eng (invited) Dr. Dr. Sudarsan J.S. Dr. Dr. Subramanian Nithiyananantham, Er. Sarala Dahal (Student), Er. Sushil Luitel, Er. Paribesh Timilsina,	ongoing	https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s13762-022-04380-9

5. Masters Students Thesis Record- 1st batch,2075

Madan Bhandari Memorial Academy Nepal Thesis Record- 1st batch,2075

S.N.	Name	Subject
1	Niraj Adhikari External; Pro.Dr.Rabindra Nath Shrestha	Analysis of the Aggregate Strength Variation at Selected Section of Biring River Basin: Under the Supervision of Er. Binod Aryal, Ph.D./ Assoc.Prof. Anjay Kumar Mishra, Ph.D.
2	Shangrila Lama External; Pro.Dr.Rabindra Nath Shrestha	Assessment of Preparedness and Awareness on Fire Safety among Management, Occupants and Concerned Authority of Selected Commercial Buildings at Birtamode, Jhapa
3	Laxmi Pd.Sapkota External; Pro.Dr.Rabindra Nath Shrestha	Impact Analysis of the Time Elapsed Between Mixing and Placing on Compressive Strength of Concrete: Under the Supervision of Er. Binod Aryal, Ph.D./ Assoc.Prof. Anjay Kumar Mishra, Ph.D.
4	Mina Yogi External; Er.Ram Krishna Sapkota	Constructability Assessment of Thabang Rural Municipality: Under the Supervision of Assoc.Prof. Anjay Kumar Mishra, Ph.D.
5	Amit Dhungana External; Er.Ram Krishna Sapkota	Assessment of Concrete Strength in Existing Structures Using Nondestructive Tests at Kachankawal Rural Municipality, Nepal: Under the Supervision of Er. Binod Aryal, Ph.D./ Assoc.Prof. Anjay Kumar Mishra, Ph.D.
6	Sujan Khadka External: Er.Jagat Kumar Shrestha, PHD	Effect of Aggregate Extracted from Different Sources on Compressive Strength of Concrete for Urlabari Municipality of Morang, Nepal: Under the Supervision of Er. Binod Aryal, Ph.D./ Assoc.Prof. Anjay Kumar Mishra, Ph.D.
7	Anju Subedi External; Er.Ram Krishna Sapkota	Performance Assessment of Solar Powered Pumping Water Supply Project in Salyan District of Nepal: Under the Supervision of Assoc.Prof. Anjay Kumar Mishra, Ph.D.
8	Rajat Pokhrel External: Dr.Er.Hare Ram Shrestha	Practicability Assessment of Smart Village Project: A Case of Sandakpur, Ilam Nepal: Under the Supervision of Assoc.Prof. Anjay Kumar Mishra, Ph.D.
9	Subash Acharya External; Er.Ram Krishna Sapkota	Construction Safety Status of Road Construction Projects in Nepal: Under the Supervision of Er. Binod Aryal, Ph.D./ Assoc.Prof. Anjay Kumar Mishra, Ph.D.
10	Hemant Gain External: Dr.Er.Hare Ram Shrestha	Risk Management Practice Adopted in Road Construction in Perspective of COVID-19 : Under the Supervision of Assoc.Prof. Anjay Kumar Mishra, Ph.D.

6. Masters Students Research publication

- (I) Mina Yogi, Mishra, A. K., & Aithal, P. S., (2022). Accessing the Compliance Standards of Selected Projects of Thabang Rural Municipality, Nepal. *International Journal of Management, Technology, and Social Sciences (IJMTS)*, 7(1), 127-140. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.47992/ijmts.2581.6012.0182>
- (II) Khadka S, Mishra AK. Effect of Fine Aggregate Sources on Compressive Strength of Cement Concrete. *J Adv Res Const Urban Arch* 2022;7(1): 9-17
- (III) Sujan Khadka, A. K. Mishra, Binod Aryal. (2022). Analysis of Coarse Aggregate Sources Effects on Compressive Strength of Cement Concrete. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6538105>
- (IV) Mishra, Anjay Kumar, Neetu Korala, Sujan Khadka, Amit Dhungana, Rajat Pokharel, Shangrila Lama, Niraj Adhikari, Shubash Acharya & Aithal, P. S., (2021). Perception Based Study of Variation Order 15278 in Building Construction Projects. *International Journal of Management, Technology, and Social Sciences (IJMTS)*, 6(2), 12-27. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5152781>
- (V) Anjay Kumar Mishra, Hemant Gain. (2022). Risk Analysis In Road Construction Using Failure Mode And Effect Analysis. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6538036>
- (VI) Hemant Gain, Mishra A. K. & Aithal P. S. (2022). Risk Management Practice Adopted in Road Construction Project. *International Journal of Management, Technology, and Social Sciences (IJMTS)*, 7(1), 21-36. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5885986>
- (VII) Gain, H. & Mishra, A.K. (2021). "Impact Of Risk Management Practice On Success Of Road Construction Project", *International Social Mentality and Researcher Thinkers Journal*, (Issn:2630-631X) 7(54): 3467-3475
- (VIII) Sapkota LP, Mishra AK, (2021). Delay Pattern Assessment in Concrete Casting. *J Adv Res Geo Sci Rem Sens*; 8(3&4): 8-17.
- (IX) Rajat Pokharel, Mishra, A. K., & Aithal, P. S., (2021). Practicability Assessment of Smart Village Project: A Case of Sandakpur Rural Municipality, Ilam Nepal. *International Journal of Management, Technology, and Social Sciences (IJMTS)*, 6(2), 265-281. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5799392>.
- (X) Dhungana A, Mishra AK, Aithal PS. Analysis of the Variation in Different Nondestructive Testing and Standards. *J Adv Res Civil Envi Engr* 2022;9(1): 1-11
- (XI) Koirala N, Sharma P, Sapkota LK et al. Variations Order of Building Construction Project a Case from Nepal. *J Adv Res Const Urban Arch* 2021;6(2): 25-33

7. Proposed Research and Development Activities of 2079/80

- [1] **Continuity of Ongoing Projects:** All the ongoing projects will be continued. More Students and faculty will be deployed. Involvement of International faculty will be shifted to new project development. Ongoing projects such as Economic Construction, Project Performance and Lean Construction will try to address new areas of research such as alternative materials to address the issues of local government for which international and local collaboration will be developed.
- [2] **Virtual Agriculture IT Industry;** The last year proposed project will be started as Virtual Agriculture IT Industry for IT Agriculture Technology Development, Improving Health , industrialization, Organic Agriculture promotion , End consumer production and Employment and tourism generation with following objectives:
- To Transform Agriculture Fields to Agriculture Industry
 - To convert Solid field into worth liquid
 - To transfer agriculture land to Data agriculture land
 - To Sale solid fields multiplying by time of product
- [3] **People Management:** One new project as people management will be started for conducting research on human resources, safety and welfare of human resources in collaboration with students and society.
- [4] **Youth incubation Centre:** Youth involvement will be assured for creating social learning management system to bring business society, youth of engineering and MBMAN at one platform under the facilitation of provincial government 1. Unnath Madan Gram Abhiyan – Adoption of villages , schools and business will be made effective through collaboration.
- [5] **Training on Research and Publication:** Training for research and publication will be continued.
- [6] **Workshop:** Workshop will be conducted @3 months to identify the local research issue and share our action research outputs among local consumers.
- [7] **Ranking of MBMAN;** Ranking of MBMAN will be promoted through research. All research scholars should be requested to Register in following Social Research/ Research Indexing websites using MBMAN official email address for ranking improvement:
- (a) ORCID-ID,
 - (b) Google Scholar,
 - (c) Research Gate,
 - (d) Elsevier's SSRN

- (e) Microsoft's Academic,
- (f) www.semanticscholar.org.
- (g) BASE.

Strength:

- Young and dynamic leadership with positive attitude of MBMAN
- Love and Affection of Public Representative and Provincial Government
- Intellectual Support from different national and international experts

Weakness:

- Less student's involvement
- Too much paper work
- Only participatory faculty involvement, not inclusive

Actions Required:

1. Students and faculty should be motivated for high efforts.
2. Pokhara University has subscribed different online journals also. PU should be requested to share their subscription of online journals with us to increase our resources access.
3. Motivation for applying Intellectual property rights should be provided.
4. Research based performance evaluation indicator should be introduced in Teachers performance evaluation.
5. Publication of research should be controlled strictly as of adopted standards given below.
 - (a) It is compulsory for all masters' students to get through plagiarism of less than 20% of the thesis and publish at least one Article in an open Access Journal with ISSN where Article should be freely Accessible to Readers. Or it should be published from any university or society.
 - (b) Copyright should be with Authors. Only publication rights can be given to publishers if journals are not from society or university.
 - (c) No or zero Article Processing Charges (APC).
 - (d) Article should have DOI preferably CrossRef/zenodo
 - (e) Submitted articles should be reviewed for Novelty, Scholarly format, Plagiarism, Grammar mistakes, & Citation-Reference matching, etc.

6. The published article should be available for Google Scholar search from the Journal immediately after publication.

To check the Journal for its suitability for publication, we go to its Current Issue (in its website). Copy the last published article title along with its author's name. Paste it into the “Google scholar search page” and if the paper is available for search and connects to its published journal page, then we consider students' publication to that Journal.